

Rt. Hon Sir Keir Starmer KCB KC
10 Downing Street
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12th May, 2025

Dear Prime Minister,

When you announced the reduction in the UK's aid budget, you pledged our country would continue nevertheless to play a key part in "supporting international efforts on global health challenges".¹

The time is now fast approaching to make good on that promise if the world is not to suffer a devastating reversal of the remarkable progress made in combating AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria, and many vaccine-preventable diseases, including measles, hepatitis B and yellow fever² – huge gains made in part thanks to British leadership that make us all proud.

As medical and public health experts working in the fields of infectious disease epidemiology and global health, we know the irreplaceable value of *Gavi The Vaccine Alliance*, and the *Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria*. These initiatives have contributed to saving millions of lives — 18.8 million³ and 65 million⁴, respectively — and could continue to do so in future, even bringing some of the *Sustainable Development Goals* within reach. But only *if* they are properly funded.^{5,6}

Sadly, Gavi's future work is in question because of a possible withdrawal of US funding, while the fight against AIDS is at risk of being set back 25 years because of donor cuts that threatens 2.9 million more deaths by the end of the decade⁷. At the same time, failing to fully fund the *Global Fund* could result in 45 million cases of malaria a year, putting huge stress on already struggling health systems.⁸

We therefore urge you, our Prime Minister, to ensure the UK continues to be a world leader when the vital *Gavi* and *Global Fund* replenishments take place in the coming months, by ensuring funding is made available in June's spending review.

The UK is one of Gavi's six original donors and has always been among its most generous. As Gordon Brown⁹ recognised at the last replenishment in 2020, it is "not just one of the most compassionate but also one of the smartest investments global leaders can make". In that year, the UK government hosted the replenishment and committed £1.65B to the "triumph of humanity over disease".¹⁰

Under your leadership, the UK will co-host the *Global Fund* replenishment later this year. As Prime Minister, you have already put AIDS centre stage when you became the first serving G7 leader to take an HIV test publicly. We urge you to continue this leadership role and inspire the world to continue in its commitments to global health before it's too late.

The Covid-19 pandemic taught us that public health threats do not respect borders and travel around the world at alarming speed if left unchecked – which means you will have the thanks of the British people, as well as people overseas, if you protect global health and vaccination programmes in the crucial spending decisions about to be made.

Kind regards,

Professor Timothy B. Hallett, FMedSci. Imperial College London
Professor Tom Churcher Imperial College London
Professor Caroline Trotter, University of Cambridge

On behalf of:

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Professor Neal Alexander	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
Dr María Algueró-Muñiz	University of Glasgow
Professor Sir Roy Anderson FRS, FMedSci	Imperial College London
Professor Martin Antonio FRCP, FRCPath, FAAS	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
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Professor Maria-Gloria Basáñez FRSB FRES	Imperial College London
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Professor Chistian Bottomly	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
Professor John Bradley	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
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Professor Fiona Burns	University College London
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Professor Adam Finn FRCP FRCPCH	University of Bristol
Professor Matthew Fisher	Imperial College London

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Professor David Goldblatt	University College London
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Professor Thomas House	University of Manchester
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Professor Richard Reeve	University of Glasgow
Professor Paul Revill	University of York
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Professor Richard White	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
Professor Alan Winston	Imperial College London
Professor Gavin J. Wright FMedSci	University of York

Footnotes

- 1 PM statement on defence spending: 25 February 2025. GOV.UK. 2025; published online Feb 25. <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/pm-statement-on-defence-spending-25-february-2025> (accessed May 7, 2025).
- 2 Li X, Mukandavire C, Cucunubá ZM, *et al.* Estimating the health impact of vaccination against ten pathogens in 98 low-income and middle-income countries from 2000 to 2030: a modelling study. *The Lancet* 2021; **397**: 398–408.
- 3 Calculating the future: how Gavi figures out how many lives vaccines have saved. <https://www.gavi.org/vaccineswork/calculating-future-how-gavi-figures-out-how-many-lives-vaccines-have-saved> (accessed May 7, 2025).
- 4 The Global Fund., Results Report 2024. Geneva, Switzerland, 2024 https://www.theglobalfund.org/media/14794/core_2024-results_report_en.pdf (accessed Oct 23, 2024).
- 5 GAVI The Vaccine Alliance., Protecting Our Future. Investment Opportunity 2026-2030. Geneva, Switzerland, 2024 <https://www.gavi.org/sites/default/files/investing/funding/resource-mobilisation/Gavi-Investment-Opportunity-2026-2030.pdf> (accessed March 9, 2025).
- 6 The Global Fund., Investment Case. Eight Replenishment 2025. 2025 https://www.theglobalfund.org/media/15380/core_2025-investment-case_report_en.pdf (accessed March 7, 2025).
- 7 Brink D ten, Martin-Hughes R, Bowring AL, *et al.* Impact of an international HIV funding crisis on HIV infections and mortality in low-income and middle-income countries: a modelling study. *The Lancet HIV* 2025; **0**. DOI:10.1016/S2352-3018(25)00074-8.
- 8 Malaria to kill 300,000 more people if critical funding not received | RBM Partnership to End Malaria. <https://endmalaria.org/news/malaria-kill-300000-more-people-if-critical-funding-not-received> (accessed May 8, 2025).
- 9 Brown G. Statement of Support. 2020. <https://www.gavi.org/sites/default/files/2020-06/Gavi-Statement-of-Support-Gordon-Brown.pdf> (accessed May 8, 2025).
- 10 World leaders make historic commitments to provide equal access to vaccines for all. 2020; published online June 15. <https://www.gavi.org/news/media-room/world-leaders-make-historic-commitments-provide-equal-access-vaccines-all> (accessed May 8, 2025).